

CONTENT, PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS, AND ASSESSMENT CRITERIA FOR THE FORMATION OF ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP SKILLS IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article covers the content, pedagogical foundations, and assessment criteria for the formation of active citizenship skills in students. The components of active citizenship skills, such as legal awareness, social activity, critical thinking, teamwork, and social responsibility, are analyzed. Also, pedagogical opportunities for the effective organization of civic education in higher education institutions in the context of globalization are revealed. The importance of interactive educational methods, project activities, volunteer activities, and social initiatives in the formation of an active citizenship position in students is substantiated. The criteria for assessing active citizenship skills include social initiative, participation in public affairs, independent decision-making, and the level of social responsibility.

Keywords: ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP, CIVIC COMPETENCE, SOCIAL ACTIVITY, LEGAL CULTURE, CIVIC EDUCATION, GLOBALIZATION, STUDENT YOUTH, INTERACTIVE METHODS, SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY, DEMOCRATIC VALUES, VOLUNTEER ACTIVITIES, CRITICAL THINKING

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